

A Comparative Study of Dermaroller and Salicylic Acid Peel in Treatment of Atrophic Acne Scars

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Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Acne scars cause significant distress to patient emotionally, as well as psychologically and are linked to depression, reduced social interactions, lower academic performance, and unemployment. Dermabrasion and lasers are costly, need proper setup, trained, skillful physician, and have significant downtime. Aim was to compare efficacy and adverse effects of minimally invasive and economic office procedures like skin needling with dermaroller, and salicylic acid peel (SA Peel), in treatment of atrophic acne scars.

Method: A randomized, open label, comparative study of skin needling with dermaroller and salicylic acid 20% peel, was carried out on 70 patients of atrophic acne scars, at the Dermatology OPD of a general hospital, at Lucknow. Each subject was treated by skin needling with dermaroller or 20% SA peel. An evaluation of improvement of scars was carried out before and 6 months after treatment, using a four scale, Qualitative Global Acne Scarring Classification of Goodman CJ, et al. Data was analyzed using SPSS, Version 17.0.

Results: In the Dermaroller group and SA Peel group, the response was 'Excellent' in 45.1% and 15.6%, 'Good' in 29% and 25%, and 'Poor' in 25.8 % and 59.3%, respectively. Adverse effects with dermaroller were edema in 25.8%, erythema in 19.3% and hyperpigmentation in 19.3%; with SA Peel, transitory erythema and hyperpigmentation were observed in 31.2% and 15.6%.

Conclusion: Dermaroller is a superior modality of treatment than 20% Salicylic acid peel in terms of efficacy and patient satisfaction. It is a safe, efficacious and cost-effective office procedure.

Keywords: Atrophic acne scar, Skin needling, Dermaroller, Salicylic acid peel, Qualitative Global Acne Scarring Classification.

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Introduction

Scarring is an unfortunate complication of acne vulgaris. It occurs early in the disease and is related to the disease severity, and delay before the treatment.[2] The scarring process can occur at any stage of acne.[6] Once scarring has occurred it is usually permanent. Acne scar may be atrophic, hypertrophic or keloidal. Atrophic scars are further divided in to 3 types namely icepick scar, rolling scar and boxcar scars.

The pathogenesis of atrophic acne scar is poorly understood. It is related to inflammatory mediators, enzymatic degradation of collagen fibers and subcutaneous fat, causing destruction of focal areas in epidermis and dermis which heal by fibrous tissue, eventually leading to various atrophic scars. [5] Acne scars cause significant distress to patient emotionally as well as psychologically and is a risk factor for suicide.[7] The scarring is linked to poor self-esteem, depression, anxiety, reduced social

interactions, body image alterations, anger, lower academic performance, and unemployment.[8,9] Instead of fading with time, the appearance of scars often worsens, with normal aging or photo damage. [10] Incidence of acne scarring in general population is reported to be from 1% to 11%.[3,4] Treatment options available for atrophic scar [12] may be medical, minimally invasive or invasive. Medical treatment such as topical retinoid and corticosteroids give slow and partial improvement.

Minimally invasive procedures include chemical peeling, skin needling with a dermaroller, chemical reconstruction of skin scars (CROSS) and tissue augmentation. CROSS may result in counter scar formation and needs a meticulous hand, punch excision and tissue augmentation requires skill. Invasive procedure such as dermabrasion requires a trained and skilled physician and a downtime of at least one week. Lasers need a proper setup and are

expensive. There is considerable interest in minimally invasive office procedures like skin needling with a dermaroller and salicylic acid peel. Skin needling with a dermaroller is a modern, cost effective, efficacious, minimally invasive office procedure. Salicylic acid 20% peel is time tested, non-invasive, and inexpensive office procedure, with hardly any downtime.

Aim was to compare efficacy and adverse effects of skin needling with dermaroller, and 20% Salicylic acid peel, in treatment of atrophic acne scars.

Material & Method

A randomized, open label, comparative study of skin needling with dermaroller and SA Peel, was carried out on patients of atrophic acne scars, at the Dermatology OPD of a Medical College & Hospital, at Lucknow. Due permission of the Institutional Ethics Committee and an informed, written consent of the subject were obtained, for the study.

A total of 70 patients, age 18-45 years, either gender, were enrolled in the study, out of which 35 (50%) were placed in Dermaroller group and 35 (50%) in Salicylic acid peel (SA Peel) group. Seven patients were lost to follow up, making the effective sample size 63; 31 in Dermaroller group and 32 in Salicylic acid peel. The final power of study was 92%.

Patients with active acne lesions, keloidal tendency, menstrual dysfunction, pregnancy, and lactation were excluded. Each subject was treated by skin needling with dermaroller or 20% SA Peel (as per the group), at an interval of 3 weeks, for a total of 4 sessions (i.e. 3 months), and subsequently, followed up for a further period of 3 months.

The data including Fitzpatrick skin type, type and number of scars, Global Acne Scar Grade of the scar before and after the treatment were recorded in a predesigned case record form. Digital photographs were taken of the scarring before treatment and at the end of the study.

Evaluation of Improvement of Scars:

Qualitative Global Acne Scarring (GAS) classification of Goodman CJ et al is a validated tool and is widely used in clinical practice and research to classify, acne scar.[11] An evaluation of improvement of scars at the end of study period of 6 months, was carried out separately by the physician, and the patient. The physician recorded the grade of scars at the first and last visit, according to GAS classification. An improvement of scarring by two grades or more was labeled as excellent response, while improvement by a single grade was

labeled as good response. In patients where scar grading remained same after the completion of the treatment, irrespective of any visible change in the facial scarring, the response was labeled as poor.

The patient evaluated improvement in scar on a ten point scale, where a rating above 7 was considered "excellent response," rating between 4 to 7 was considered a "good" response and rating below 4 "poor" response.

Procedure:

- In the **Dermaroller group**, skin needling was carried by rolling a sterile dermaroller (impregnated with 192 needles, size 1.5 mm x 0.25mm), across the affected skin, with uniform pressure. The dermaroller was rolled four times, in each of the four directions (horizontally, vertically, diagonally right and diagonally left), for a total of 16 passes. The treated area demonstrated uniform, pinpoint bleeding, through thousands of micro puncture sites. Postoperatively strict photo-protection was advised with sun screen.
- In the **Salicylic Acid Peel group**, 20% peel was applied with the help of a flat brush, smooth strokes applied sequentially on the face (unit wise - forehead, right cheek, chin, left cheek, glabella, nose, perioral area, upper and lower eyelids), to elicit pseudo-frosting. The pseudo-frost was wiped away with cold water after 10 minutes, or patient was asked to wash it away. The patient was advised strict photo-protection, with sunscreen and emollients.

Statistical analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences), Version 17.0. The values were represented in number (%) and Mean \pm SD. Chi square test of proportion and association was used for test of the equality of proportion and relationship between the two attributes. To test the significance of two means, the student 't' test was used. To compare the change in a parameter at two different time intervals, paired "t" test was used. Non parametric Wilcoxon signed rank test was used for test of change of grading before and after the treatment. Mann-Whitney u test was used for comparison of data and evaluation of results. 'p' value less than 0.05 was considered to be a statistically significant change; p <0.05 significant, <0.01 highly significant, and <0.001 very highly significant.

Results

In the Dermaroller group 31 out 35 subjects, and in Salicylic acid peel (SA Peel) group 32 out of 35 subjects, completed the study.

Table 1: Demographic profile of patients of atrophic acne scar

Feature		Dermaroller (n=32)	SA Peel (n=31)
Age	≤20 yrs	3 (9.7%)	3 (9.4%)
	21-30 yrs	25 (80.6%)	28 (87.5%)
	>30 yrs	3 (9.7%)	1 (3.1%)
Gender	Male	9 (29.0%)	13 (40.6%)
	Female	22 (71.0%)	19 (59.4%)

'p' value for age 0.562 and for gender 0.335

The age of patients ranged from 19 yrs to 36 yrs, 53 (84.1%) were between 21-30 years of age and male to female ratio was 1:1.8. Mean age of patients in Dermaroller group was 25.45 years and in SA Peel group, 24.66 years.

Table 2: Fitzpatrick Skin type and duration of scar

Feature		Dermaroller (n=31)	SA Peel (n=32)
Fitzpatrick Skin type	IV	13 (41.9%)	16 (50.0%)
	V	18 (58.1%)	16 (50.0%)
Duration of scars	<5 Yrs	14 (45.2%)	19 (59.4%)
	5-10 Yrs	12 (38.7%)	11 (34.4%)
	>10 Yrs	5 (16.1%)	2 (6.3%)

'p' value for Skin type 0.521, and duration of scars 0.355

Duration of scars was seen to be less than 5 years in majority (52.4%) of cases. The baseline Qualitative Global Acne scarring grading profile in either group was comparable.

Table 3: Global Acne Scarring Grade at Baseline

SN	Grade	Dermaroller (n=31)	SA Peel (n=32)
1.	I	1(3.2%)	3 (9.4%)
2.	II	8 (25.8%)	11(34.4%)
3.	III	15 (48.4%)	14 (43.8%)
4.	IV	7 (22.6%)	4 (12.5%)

$z=1.452$; $p=0.146$, (Mann-Whitney U test)

After a period of 6 months from initiation of the treatment, improvement in the grade of acne scars was assessed.

Table 4: Change in Global Acne Scarring Grade at 6 months

No. of patients (n=31)	Grade of the scar before treatment	Grade of the scar after treatment				
		I	II	III	IV	Complete resolution
Dermaroller						
1 (3.2%)	I	0	0	0	0	1
8 (25.8%)	II	6	2	0	0	0
15 (48.4%)	III	11	2	2	0	0
7 (22.6%)	IV	2	1	0	4	0
Statistical significance of change: $z=4.30$; $p<0.001$ (Highly significant) Wilcoxon signed rank test						
SA Peel						
3	I	0	0	0	0	3
5	II	3	3	0	0	5
12	III	0	2	12	0	0
4	IV	0	0	0	4	0
	Total	3	5	12	4	8
Statistical significance of change: $z=3.286$; $p=0.001$ (Highly significant) Wilcoxon signed rank test						

Description required

Table 5: Physician and the Patient Assessment at 6 months

Satisfaction	Dermaroller (n=31)		SA Peel (n=32)	
	Physician	Patient	Physician	Patient
Excellent	14 (45.2%)	5 (15.6%)	6 (18.8%)	15 (48.4%)
Good	9 (29.0%)	8 (25.0%)	8 (25.0%)	9 (29.0%)
Poor	8 (25.8%)	19 (59.4%)	18 (56.3%)	7 (22.6%)

Physician's evaluation: $\chi^2=8.790$; $*p=0.012$ (highly significant) Chi square test; Patient's evaluation: $\chi^2=8.742$; $p=0.013$ (highly significant) Chi square test.

Proportion of those with good to excellent response as evaluated by the physician and the patient was significantly higher in Dermaroller (77.4% & 74.2%) as compared to that in SA peel (43.7% & 40.6%). In the Dermaroller group, an excellent response was observed in 14 (45.2%), good in 9 (29%) and poor in 8 (25.8%). Overall the improvement in grade of scars was statistically highly

significant ($p<0.001$). In Salicylic acid peel, excellent response was observed in 5 (15.6%), good in 8 (25%), while poor in 19 (59.4%). The improvement in grade of scars was statistically highly significant ($p=0.001$).

The assessment in the improvement of the scar was carried out by the physician by assessing the change in Qualitative Global Acne Scarring Grade. The patient judged their response on a ten point scale as excellent (score > 7), good (score 4-7) or poor (score < 4). The adverse effects observed with either treatment during the study period.

Table 6: Adverse Effects

Side effect	Dermaroller (n=31)	SA Peel (n=32)	Statistical significance	
Edema	8 (25.8%)	0 (0.0)	0.002*	9.459*
Erythema	6 (19.4%)	10 (31.3%)	0.278	1.176
Hyper- pigmentation	6 (19.4%)	5 (15.6%)	0.697	0.152
Secondary infection	0	0		

* $p=0.002$ for edema (highly significant)

In Dermaroller group edema was seen in 25.8% erythema in 19.4%, and hyperpigmentation in 19.4% and cases; in SA Peel group transient erythema and hyperpigmentation were seen in 31.3% and 15.6% respectively, none developed edema.

Grade 3 scars were most common at baseline and at the end of study, most of the scars improved to grade 1 in Dermaroller group while in SA Peel mild or no change was observed. No long term complications were seen.

Discussion

The treatment of atrophic acne scars by skin needling with a dermaroller, and 20% Salicylic acid peel (SA Peel), are minimally invasive office procedures. Outcome of the treatment by either of the modality, was assessed using the change in Qualitative Global Acne Scarring (GAS) Grade, at the end of 6 months from initiation of the treatment.

In the present study skin needling by dermaroller revealed good to excellent response in majority, 74.2% and poor response in 25.8% of subjects. On correlating the improvement in grade of scars, it was observed that dermaroller gave good result in 100% patients of grade 1 scars, 75% patients of grade 2 scars, 73.3% patients of grade 3 scars. In patients with grade 4 scars 42.8% of patients showed moderate improvement. The result conforms the observations of Imran Majid, who reported good to excellent response in majority of patients of grade 2 and grade 3 atrophic acne scars, and poor response in majority of patients with grade 4 scars.[6]

SA Peel showed good to excellent response in 40.6% and poor response in 59.4% of subjects. On correlating the improvement in various grade of acne scars it was observed that with SA Peel, 100%

of patients of grade 1 scars showed excellent improvement, 72.6% of patients with grade 2 scars showed good results, 85.7% of patients with grade 3 scars and 100% of patients with grade 4 showed poor result. Grime P E, also observed resolution of 100% of grade 1 scars with salicylic acid peel.[9] S Purohit, et al observed rapid improvement in hyperpigmented macular scars (Grade 1) with SA Peel, but a poor response in deep scars.[10]

Adverse effects were observed 64.6% patients treated with dermaroller. They were edema in 25.8%, erythema in 19.3% and hyperpigmentation in 19.3% of patients. The findings are similar to the study by Dogra S, et al who reported hyperpigmentation in 16.6% of patients. [8] In SA Peel group, transient erythema was observed in 31.3% and hyperpigmentation in 15.6% of patients. Patients had reduced incidence of acne eruptions during the study. The peeling of skin 3 to 4 days after the SA Peel was of concern in few patients.

It was noted in this study and also reported by G. Fabbrocini, et al that dermaroller gave an aesthetic improvement, in just two sessions. The beneficial effect of dermaroller was immediate, and the improvement continued for a period of 12 months with reduction in the depth of scars and pigmentation. [7] Dermaroller showed added advantages of skin rejuvenation, reduced fine lines, pores and freckles, improved skin color and texture. The limitations were burning and pain during the procedure. In the present study patient satisfaction in the Dermaroller group was 77.4% which is similar to the observation by Dogra S, et al. [8] Patient satisfaction for aesthetic improvement of the scars in SA Peel group was 43.8%.

The superior response of dermaroller in atrophic acne scar can be attributed to neocollagenesis and

neovascularization following multiple superficial micro bruises extending to superficial dermis. The salicylic acid peel acts via destruction of covalently linked intercellular lipids, causing exfoliation of epidermis.

Conclusions

Dermaroller gives good to excellent response in majority of patients with grade 1 to grade 3 scars while salicylic acid peel gives good to excellent response only in grade 1 and grade 2 scars.

Patient satisfaction is better with the dermaroller as compared to the salicylic acid peel.

The skin needling with dermaroller is a simple, low cost, minimally invasive, efficacious office procedure for atrophic acne scars.

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